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The Accordion as a Metaphorical
Acoustic Synthesizer

in Electroacoustic Music.

An Outline of Extended Performance
Techniques Based on the Composer's
Own Works

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1. Introduction and Discussion of Four Groups of Performance and Production Techniques

In traditional classification (Curt Sachs and Erich von Hornbostel), the accordion is an aerophone, and its sounds are produced by reeds in which the airstream (generated by the bellows) sets off a series of impulses (vibrations). In the music of the second half of the twentieth century, it gained a special status, becoming a fully recognized concert instrument used both in solo repertoire and with orchestral or electronic accompaniment. Many composers and performers have undertaken interesting and innovative experiments that have significantly expanded its sonic palette. The timbral qualities of the accordion and the richness of its performance techniques make it an instrument particularly attractive from the perspective of contemporary music, including electroacoustic music. Its sound integrates relatively easily with the electronic layer, offering extensive possibilities for composers and performers. The standard, implicitly classical, capabilities of the accordion can be expanded through a range of contemporary methods, which may be divided into the following groups:

1. Extended performance techniques involving a non-orthodox treatment of the instrument, including, on the one hand, the search for new playing methods and modifications of fundamental tones (overblowing / pitch bending), and on the other, the production of sounds in ways other than traditional ones – using mechanical elements, tapping on the keyboard or buttons, employing register switches, or treating the bellows and body percussively, etc.
2. The extraction of particular timbral aspects through various miking techniques – close, distant (or a mix of both), the use of contact microphones mounted in different locations – and, subsequently, appropriate amplification and spatial distribution of the sound. It should be emphasized that at this stage we are referring exclusively to the pure accordion sound, not electronically processed in any way.
3. The use of electronic means to process the material obtained from microphones, thereby expanding the palette with tones unattainable by the acoustic instrument itself, yet derived from it. In such cases, the full range of electronic tools may be employed, including filters, ring modulation, spectral shifters, granular processing, pitch shifting, delay, and many others.
4. The use of accordion recordings to construct the electronic layer of a composition, which is then played back as an audio track (tape). In this case, extensive transformations and editing may be applied, fundamentally altering the character of the resulting sound or enabling the creation of a kind of alter ego of the real instrument, with which the performer engages in dialogue during the live performance.

In the works I have composed for accordion with an electronic layer, or with real-time electronic processing, I have employed techniques belonging to each of the four groups listed above. I will discuss these in more detail in the following part of the paper, focusing on the following compositions:

- *Soundscape with the Fall of Icarus* (2018) for accordion, electronics, and computer,
- live-performed music for the silent film *Nosferatu – A Symphony of Horror* (*Nosferatu, eine Symphonie des Grauens*), directed by Friedrich Wilhelm Murnau – the project, realized jointly with Paweł Zagańczyk, was presented in 2018 at the Kraków Accordion Festival,
- *Golem XXI* (2019) for accordion, piano, other optional instruments and sound objects, electronics, and computer – a multimedia performance prepared together with Paweł Zagańczyk for the Zbliżenia Festival,
- *More Equal Than Others* (2019) for accordion and computer,
- *4 Sketches for 4 Sides of the World* (2021) – miniatures for accordion and computer, two of which (*East* and *North*) are my own works, while the remaining two (*South* and *West*) are by

2. Scenarios Applied in the Process of Composing for Accordion and Electronics

When composing works for accordion and tape, or with live electronics, I generally followed two different scenarios. The first, used in *Soundscape with the Fall of Icarus*, consisted of first completing the entire electronic layer, which was largely created from processed accordion recordings, including those made using contact microphones, allowing for the extraction of specific timbral qualities. This material was supplemented with a limited number of synthetically generated sounds.

A somewhat similar approach formed the basis of the music for *Nosferatu*. In this case, a foundational electronic layer synchronized with the on-screen events was created first, and upon this foundation – together with Paweł Zagańczyk – we performed live during the screening: I on synthesizers, prepared piano, and effects, and Paweł on accordion and acoustic sound objects. The multimedia performance *Golem XXI*, inspired by the story told in Gustav Meyrink's novel *Golem (Der Golem, 1915)*, was created in a similar manner, although in this case the instrumentation was further expanded to include additional objects used jointly with Paweł Zagańczyk.

The second type of scenario was employed in *More Equal Than Others* and *4 Sketches for 4 Sides of the World*. In this case, the instrumental part was written first, already with the assumption that it would be accompanied by an electronic layer (tape). The part was then recorded by the performer, and the recording served as the basis for constructing the tape layer, built overwhelmingly from various transformations of the instrumental recordings, with a certain addition of synthesizer sounds.

In the process of creating the electronic layer for all my compositions for accordion and tape, I employed a range of contemporary sound-processing techniques. In particular, these included digital tools based on phase vocoder technology, as well as granular processors, filters, loopers, and modulation effects (phaser, chorus, flanger). The resulting material was cut into fragments of varying lengths, assigned an appropriate dynamic profile, multiplied by layering multiple tracks, and finally edited in order to achieve the final result characterized by proper dramaturgy. In terms of timbre, this material covered a relatively broad spectrum, ranging from sounds clearly revealing their origin – referring to the pure timbre of the accordion – to distinctly synthetic, electronic textures in which it is difficult to discern features of the original source. The combination of all these elements creates the impression of a radical expansion of the accordion's capabilities, both through the addition of its alter ego in the tape layer and through the extensive transformations of the source material. In the case of *Soundscape with the Fall of Icarus*, these transformations occur not only in the tape layer but are also carried out live, taking the instrumental part as their point of departure.

Golem XXI (2019)

for accordion, live electronics, objects and tape

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♩ = 60
1:20

R
Acc.
L

ff nuty dowolnej wysokości

mf
nuty dowolnej wysokości
grać rytmicznie, pod taśmę

p *mp*

improwizacja, wysokości dźwięku, wartości nut aproksymatywne (grać pod taśmę)

The first page of the score of the composition Golem XXI – the accordion part is written very generally, conventionally, because the musician has a lot of freedom to improvise.

3. Soundscape with the Fall of Icarus (2018)

In the case of the composition *Soundscape with the Fall of Icarus*, similarly to *More Equal than Others* and *4 Sketches for the 4 Sides of the World*, an aspect of absolutely crucial importance is very strict adherence to timing. For this reason, performing these works requires the performer to use headphones and a click signal that helps execute the instrumental part with precision. Each sound must have its place and must occur in correlation with events unfolding in the electronic layer (tape), or with live effects activated at a given moment in time. Otherwise, if this condition is not fulfilled, the compositional structure will disintegrate.

This is, of course, a requirement that poses a considerable challenge for the performer, since they must simultaneously follow the score, the timeline, and listen to the electronic layer as well as the click signal. For this reason, I recommend placing a large monitor on stage showing the elapsed time from the beginning of the piece. Sometimes it is also helpful to display the DAW session from which the tape part is played. By seeing the waveform – with certain characteristic elements such as dynamic peaks – as well as the moving vertical playhead, the performer immediately knows which moment of the composition they are in and what may happen next. This is not easy and requires practice; nevertheless, once this method is mastered, performing this type of repertoire becomes easier.

For the performer, it is a great convenience to be able to preview the DAW project, which contains the electronic part and live effects – this allows them to see where they are currently.

Soundscape with the Fall of Icarus was composed in 2018 for Paweł Zagańczyk and is an example of a sonoristic treatment of the accordion while preserving its natural sound and making it the solo instrument accompanied by a tape part that functions here as a kind of electronic orchestra.

The title of the piece and its aesthetic refer to the painting attributed (some experts believe it is a copy of a lost original) to the Netherlandish painter Pieter Bruegel the Elder, painted around 1557 and currently housed in the Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium in Brussels.

To integrate the accordion and the tape more closely (as a reminder – largely built from processed

recordings of the instrument), a third component/layer was added: live electronic effects that process the instrumental part.

In this piece, the performer must above all adhere very strictly to timing, playing with a click while following the clock/measure counter. Each sound must be played at a specific moment so that it synchronizes with the tape and the programmed effects placed on DAW tracks and controlled via automation.

In contrast, within the performance and articulation sphere the accordionist has a certain degree of freedom and may – within limits – choose means for modifying the instrument's tone, such as pitch bends. According to the notation, the performer also applies a number of extended techniques that expand the palette of sounds. In particular:

- opening and closing the bellows to obtain the effect of a rustling wind or sea waves – for example measures 7–17,
- percussive tapping on the buttons with varying force and intensity, from *p* to *ff* – for example measures 141–142 (and beyond),
- striking the bellows with the fist in order to produce muted knocks – for example measures 298–305,
- rubbing the bellows and wooden elements of the accordion with the bristles of a brush (the use of several brushes of different sizes is permitted) to obtain noises of varying intensity – for example measures 202–211,
- rubbing the brush bristles against metal elements – for example measures 240–248,
- tapping the bellows and wooden parts with a wooden spoon, a percussion stick, or the handle of a brush – for example measures 20–21,
- gently tapping metal parts with a wooden spoon, percussion stick, or brush handle – in this case, in the section spanning measures 306–312 the performer should follow the polyrhythmic structure on the tape.

As can be seen from the above description, the performer not only plays the accordion in a more or less traditional manner but also uses additional tools such as brushes of various sizes and bristle hardness, wooden spoons, or percussion sticks. The descriptive section of the score contains instructions on how these additional accessories should be used.

Furthermore, the sound of the instrument captured by microphones is additionally processed electronically in real time. Various effects are employed, in particular:

- low-pass and high-pass filters controlled by LFOs of different frequencies,
- modulation effects such as phaser, chorus, and flanger,
- pitch shifting and formant shifting,
- delay,
- tremolo,
- granular processing involving sampling the input sound, cutting it into fragments, and randomly scattering them, with key parameters modulated by LFOs,
- as well as reverberation (with different decay times).

The performer uses many unconventional techniques, including rubbing the body of the instrument with various brushes and brushes.

Performing a composition with tape and live electronics often requires the composer's presence on stage.

6:24 193 194 195 196 6:32

6:32 197 198 199 200 6:40

6:40 201 202 203 204 6:48

FX4 = -3dB
fade in end

6:48 205 206 207 208 6:56

6:56 209 210 211 212 7:04

7:04 213 214 215 216 7:12

FX4 = OFF

FX3 = -12dB

FX3 = OFF

hairs on bellows

mf

fff

wood on bellows

A fragment of the piece's score – with marked sections where the instrument should be rubbed with various objects.

4. More Equal Than Others (2019)

An example of an advanced coexistence between the electronic layer (largely built from processed recordings of the accordion) and the instrumental part is the piece *More Equal Than Others* from 2019. It was written for Krzysztof Olczak on the occasion of the 40th anniversary of his artistic work in Gdańsk.

The title of the composition is a quotation from George Orwell's novel *Animal Farm: A Fairy Story*.

At the very beginning, in measures 1–11, one can hear the note E contra (the lowest pitch of the accordion) repeated three times. Each time the tone is half as long and features vibrato twice as fast. In the tape layer it is accompanied by the same pitch with modulation effects and filtering, as well as short percussive interventions of the synthesizer.

The symbiosis of the acoustic tone – the reed – with its electronic counterpart is therefore quite advanced.

The piece is based on contrasting fragments belonging to two types: on the one hand passages built on long sustained tones of the instrument accompanied by a coherent electronic layer; on the other hand distinctly rhythmic sections in which the accordion plays together with its electronic alter ego as if driven by a sequencer rather than the performer's hand.

The effect of a certain mechanical quality is intentional here and requires very strict adherence to the grid, that is, playing with a click.

Examples of such rhythmic structures can be found in measures 56–59. Beginning with measure 133 a percussive section starts, lasting until the end of measure 158. The rhythmic percussive sounds are produced by striking the buttons of the left-hand manual; they should be loud and strong – if necessary, their level may be reinforced with appropriate amplification.

At the same time, the right hand performs rhythmic glissandi on the keys (or buttons) of the right-hand manual – alternating up and down in successive measures. In this section the performer does not operate the bellows and the accordion effectively becomes a percussion instrument.

The piece also employs the effect of juxtaposing the sound of the accordion with an identical sound obtained through analysis and resynthesis in a processor based on phase-vocoder technology. This sound initially has the same pitch as the instrumental tone and then gradually moves away from it upward through a smooth glissando.

The listener therefore has the impression that the instrument sounds in a way that an acoustic accordion would technically not be capable of producing.

This is in fact a frequently used technique in the composition, thanks to which the electronic layer adds a kind of artifacts and sounds that resemble accordion tones but already lie beyond the reach of the acoustic instrument.

In the final section of the composition, temporally stretched instrumental tones are accompanied by related electronic structures enriched with a spatial modulation effect. As a result, the listener has the impression that the pure tone of the instrument dissolves in space, becoming increasingly fuller and wider in subjective perception.

Performing More Equal Than Others requires two microphones and headphones with a click signal.

A computer monitor that displays the time, ticks, and tape progress is also recommended.

165

p bellows shake *f* *p* legato

8^{vb}

169

legato *mf* *p* *mp*

8^{vb}

173

f non legato *mf*

8^{vb}

177

f non legato legato

181

legato *mp*

185

f *non legato* *mf*

189

vibrato allegro* non vibrato

193

pp *mp*

197

f *mp* *mp* *f* *mp*

vibrato lento** vibrato moderato**

loco

201

pp

205

mp *f* *f* *f*

vibrato moderato** vibrato lento**

* / ** vibrato lewą(*) lub prawą(**) ręką / perform vibrato with left(*) or right(**) hand

5. 4 Sketches for the 4 Sides of the World

In the case of this piece – or more precisely the miniatures that compose it – a noteworthy element is a special method of microphone placement on the accordion, thanks to which particular sonic aspects of the instrument can be revealed.

This applies especially to the left-hand manual, which among other functions is used to produce deep bass tones. Close microphone placement makes the pure tone sound almost like that of a synthesizer, even without special electronic processing, allowing it to integrate well with the electronic layer.

Of course, an instrument amplified in this way will sound somewhat unnatural, which may pose a certain challenge for listeners accustomed to the acoustic and unmodified timbre of the instrument.

However, in the case of this cycle of miniatures it was a conscious and intentional approach, allowing for the creation of a specific sonic effect resulting from the combination of the closely miked accordion and the electronic layer.

Close miking (using clip-on microphones) of the accordion allows for the production of deep tones.

Four Sketches for Four Sides of the World - East
for accordion and computer

$\text{♩} = 120$

loco

8^{va}

bellows stroke

body knock

8^{va}

8^{va}

p

switch click

switch click

BB

9

key click

8^{va}

8^{va}

pp *mp*

vibrato allegro

bellows stroke

8^{va}

14

8^{va}

8^{va}

p *mp*

air button

8^{va}

22

air button

f

ricochet

ricochet

pp

8^{va}

28

8^{va}

8^{va}

air button

mp

Notes / Uwagi:

Vibrato allegro (bar 12) with right hand / Vibrato allegro (takt 12) prawą ręką

First page of the score of the miniature East / East.

Four Sketches for Four Sides of the World - North
for accordion and computer

$\text{♩} = 100$

loco

1 8^{va} mp f mp f mp 8^{va}

BB bellows shake bellows shake

4 8^{va} mp f mp f

bellows shake bellows shake

7 8^{va} mp p

8^{ob}

13 8^{va} ppp $< p$

21 8^{va} mp 8^{va}

First page of the score of the miniature North / North.

6. Conclusion

There is no doubt that the accordion is an instrument that already in itself offers enormous sonic possibilities, allowing performers to employ a wide range of techniques and achieve very diverse sound results.

This allows composers to create works that take advantage of these specific qualities. Moreover, although the concert accordion is today a widely recognized instrument, there is still considerable room for experimentation, the search for new means of expression, and the expansion of its sonic possibilities.

As mentioned at the beginning, the instrument is characterized by a specific timbre that integrates very well with the electronic environment. For this reason, it is an excellent tool for composers of electroacoustic music who are interested in writing works for solo instrument with tape or live electronics.

It is also an instrument that offers great opportunities for improvising musicians, making it even more attractive for contemporary creators.

One can therefore hope that the accordion will continue to be explored by artists working in the field of electroacoustic music and that this exploration will result in new and intriguing compositions.

In the future, I plan to compose further works of this type and to seek new ways of integrating the accordion part within them.

Author

Dariusz Mazurowski – a Polish composer of electroacoustic music, producer, and performer based in Gdańsk. He creates acousmatic works, compositions for instruments and electronics, as well as projects in the field of sound installations and improvised electroacoustic music. In his artistic practice, he combines analog instrumentation and self-designed electronic constructions with digital technology, employing, among other techniques, live electronics, multichannel sound diffusion, and methods of processing and transforming concrete sound material.

His works have been presented at numerous international electroacoustic music festivals across Europe, the Americas, and Asia, and have been broadcast by radio stations worldwide. He is the author of publications devoted to contemporary music and technological issues, a participant in academic conferences and workshops, and an active member of the Polish Society for Electroacoustic Music (PSeME).

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